

Pt. II—Recreating the Ancient Elamite-Mesopotamian *Tigidla* Lute

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2.1: The Revival and Reconstruction of Ancient Music

Reconstruction of historical musical instruments has become an increasingly popular and important area in music archaeology and in popular culture. This is seen perhaps most prominently in the burgeoning historical lyre community, spurred on by Einar Selvik's scores for the hit TV show *Vikings* and by strides made in the understanding of ancient Greek music theory and culture. From these two currents have sprung international communities of musicians, composers, luthiers professional and amateur, and listeners enchanted by the idea of recreating music and instruments of the ancient Greeks and Egyptians and Medieval Europe that have been extinct for centuries.

These reconstruction movements rely on three primary data sources: archaeological finds of preserved instruments, iconographic representations of musical instruments, and textual notices or descriptions of instruments and music. In some fortunate cases, as with ancient Egyptian instruments, a number of lutes, harps, and wind instruments have been unearthed that allow us to see more or less precisely how the Egyptians actually made them. Much of this data is corroborated by the remarkably—though not fully—faithful depictions of these instruments in Egyptian tomb paintings and other artworks. On the other hand, textual mentions of instruments and music are virtually non-existent in pre-Hellenistic Egyptian literature so certain crucial aspects of music like tuning systems and even instrument names are a matter of, at best, educated guesswork.

In the cases of Egypt's Bronze Age contemporaries in Syria, Anatolia, Mesopotamia and Elam, virtually no instruments have been found outside the famous harps and lyres of the 'Royal tombs of Ur', excavated by Sir Leonard Woolley in the 1920s. The many

iconographic depictions of instruments from these regions were, for the most part, not rendered with anything like the Egyptians' attention to detail and often survive only in fragmentary condition and without archaeological context. Mesopotamian lexical lists and royal praise poems have furnished many instrument names, some sociological information, and a few poetic allusions, but to date scholars have been able to (tentatively) link only a few of these names to iconographic representations.¹

This situation, where only primary-yet-indirect sources exist, presents an array of difficulties when it comes to designing a faithful, accurate reconstruction of these ancient musical instruments. The project that I and my colleague Sepideh Khaksar have embarked on—recreating a Bronze Age lute of the Elamite and Mesopotamian type, using mostly Elamite iconography of the 2nd half of the 2nd millennium BCE²—has been a repeated encounter with semiotic fragmentation, in the often fragmented physical condition of artifacts as well as the images' artistic qualities. Fine, accurate details of lute designs are entirely missing, as it was arguably rarely the artists' intent to convey that level of pictorial information. Instead, they mostly contain only that information needed to communicate to their viewers the central idea of the image. In other words, when an ancient image-maker sculpted a lute in a figure's arms, usually this figure plays the central visual and semiotic role and the lute acts more as an attribute.

For example, many depictions of the Hindu deities Śiva or Sarasvatī present them with the Indic string instrument *vīṇā*. The deities serve as the focal point for the viewers' contemplations or adorations but the instruments—and any other objects they may carry—are their attributes, extensions of the deities' qualities and meanings, without which the deities would be in some sense incomplete. A finely-wrought statue of Sarasvatī may display her *vīṇā* in exquisite detail, but a piece made for more popular markets such as

¹ Terms like *algar*, *sammi*, and *balag* are particularly controversial and have been interpreted to refer to harps, lyres, or various kinds of percussion. See Duchesne-Guillemin 1970; Lawergren and Gurney 1987; Michalowski 2010; and Mirelman 2015.

² All of these artifacts are currently housed at either the National Museum of Iran in Teheran or at Le Louvre in Paris, France.

religious pilgrims or household altars will typically render the *vīṇā* in broad strokes, leaving it to the viewer's imagination to 'fill in the gaps'. The viewer need only understand what the instrument is supposed to be in order to recall what it means in relation to the goddess they stand before.

In the case of the Elamite artifacts, the nature of their artistic medium—terracotta plaques mass-produced from carved molds—and the objects' intended uses discouraged fine modeling and/or rendered such detailing redundant.³

This article represents my role in this collaboration between Sepideh and I. It will describe the process I went through in designing and crafting a reconstruction of the Elamite/Mesopotamian lute. I based this work on the archaeological and sociological data painstakingly collated and graciously provided by Sepideh. I will give an account of the issues resulting from the limitations of our sources and the decisions I made to work around them; our debates over how to interpret the iconographic information; the models I chose as guides for various design elements and why I chose them, and what I learned from these models. Finally, I will analyze the finished first prototype, what elements worked or did not, and ideas/areas for further experimentation and refinement in future versions of these lutes. I have envisaged this as an on-going and evolving project to create other versions of these lutes as well as reconstructions of other species of ancient string instruments.

Although all the images upon which I based my reconstruction came from the Elamite cultural region I broadly refer to the instrument as an Elamite-Mesopotamian long neck lute, which requires some clarification. First, the earliest attested lutes in the Ancient Near East appear in the Akkadian era, c. 2334 BCE. By the Ur III period (22nd-21st centuries BCE) lutes apparently formed part of the Mesopotamian kings' musical education.⁴ Lutes first appear in Elamite artifacts in the early 2nd millennium BCE, albeit in a different social context and with a different form than their Mesopotamian contemporaries. As Sepideh relates, the later Bronze Age iconography portrays a distinctly other

³ These are by and large popular objects not necessarily meant for long-term use.

⁴Castellino 1972, pp. 47-50.

kind of lute—with a longer neck and smaller body—and player—a dwarfish male figure. This figure recalls figures occasionally seen already in some Old Babylonian banquet scenes from Mesopotamia and Syria.

Also, the Mesopotamian lexical list OB Nippar Ura 01, in particular, contains a plethora of musical instrument names including those for a variety of regional forms of lutes.⁵ One of these, *tigidla*, occurs with several apparent subtypes such as a *tigidla* of Dilmun, of ‘the highlands’, a ‘traveler’s’ *tigidla*, a type ‘with three strings’, and, most importantly, a *tigidla* of Elam.

All these factors therefore, in my view, make it probable that lutes were a Mesopotamian cultural import to due to the various phases of intense cultural and political contacts between the two polities. One can assume these regional forms were differentiated by equally regional design, construction, and musical traditions. Although I agree with Sepideh on this point, and that the Elamite images display a lack of standardization in the lutes’ designs, it is my opinion that these images available do not provide enough unambiguous information on what these differences may have been or looked like to form any conclusions on many design details.

2.2: Models Ancient and Modern for the Elamite-Mesopotamian Lute

Because of this dearth of detailed information I decided to look to three other sources as models for how to approach various design issues for the reconstruction: extant specimens of Egyptian New Kingdom (c. 1550-c. 1077 BCE) lutes; the modern lutes played throughout the West African Sahel by the bards known as *jeli* (sg.; pl. *jeliw*)⁶ and called by various names such as *ngoni*, and a class of modern lutes played mostly by the Berbers and Touareg in Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia known as *gunibri* and *lotar/loutar*. The two modern categories seem to have organological and possibly historical

⁵ <http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/dcclt/pager>, ‘Old Babylonian>Thematic Word Lists>OB Nippar Ura 01’. In. 613-616; accessed 22 Mar. 2022. See also Krispijn 2010, p. 148.

⁶Charry 1996; 2000.

relationships to the Egyptian lutes, although a direct line of transmission is as yet unproven.⁷

It may surprise some that I did not consider modern Iranian lutes like *tanbūr*, *setar* or *dutār* as potential models; I reasoned that the New Kingdom specimens constituted, for reasons discussed below, the closest morphological types to the Elamite-Mesopotamian lutes while the *tanbūr* etc. are attested, at least by names, nearly 1,500 years later. They may well have thus undergone significant morphological alterations, such as wooden soundboards and tuning pegs, from their putative Bronze Age Near Eastern ancestors. Nevertheless, I intend to experiment with such features on future versions of the Elamite-Mesopotamian lute.

2.3: The Egyptian New Kingdom Lute

Although ancient Egypt had sophisticated harps by the onset of the Old Kingdom (c. 2686-2181 BCE), lutes and lyres are not attested until c.1600 BCE. In the New Kingdom lutes are frequently depicted in tomb paintings, relief carvings, and women's jewelry and accessories. More importantly for this study, archaeologists have unearthed several actual lutes, the one found in the tomb of Harnosē, who lived during the reign of Pharaoh Hatshepsut (c. 1507-1458 BCE) and was singer to her chief architect Senenmut, being perhaps the most famous and the best preserved (*Pl. 2.3.1*).⁸ Lutes were not endemic to Egypt but imported probably via diplomatic gifts and exchanges of musicians—even entire orchestras—and other artisans from Syria, Mesopotamia, and Anatolia to Egypt's north.⁹ As such, I contend that the Egyptian lute likely retained a significant amount of as its northern ancestors' morphological traits.

⁷ Though not necessarily a social or cultural relationship, as their role in Sahelian societies is markedly different from that of lutes in New Kingdom Egypt.

⁸ Scott 1944.

⁹ See Podany 2012, pp. 40-41, 73, 108, 229.

Pl. 2.3.1: Lute of Harnosě. Source: N. E. Scott 1944, p. 161.

However, given the likelihood of numerous genera and species of northern lutes, with design variations that remain mostly unknown to us, we cannot know how faithfully the Egyptian lutes kept to their ‘originals’, if there was a particular northern species introduced to Egypt or many, or to what degree, if any, the Egyptians naturalized the instrument by adding their own touches and innovations to its construction. Nevertheless, as the Egyptian artifacts constitute the nearest surviving relations to the Elamite and Mesopotamian instruments they hold great value as a source of organological information.

Two distinct types of Egyptian lutes existed (Pl. 2.3.2),¹⁰ both of the category of long necked type,¹¹ and both archaeologically represented. Type A displays a rounded body, sometimes made from tortoise shell but more commonly of carved wood, a long, narrow neck and two strings. The respective lengths of Type A’s resonator and neck display an average ratio to each other of .34:1. The second, Type B, exemplified by the Harnosě lute, features a long, narrow, oblong resonator, a neck similar to that of Type B but in an average ratio of .53:1 with the resonator, and with two or three strings.

¹⁰ Whose names are unknown although several possibilities have been offered (see Manniche 1992, p. 45). In the early 20th century it was argued they were called *nefer*, due to the similarity of the hieroglyph for this word to the lutes’ outline but this theory has since been discarded.

¹¹ As defined by Hornbostel and Sachs 1961, pp. 22-23. NB a third type is attested but from a later period (1st millennium BCE) whereas Types A and B are contemporaneous to the Elamite and Mesopotamian images; Eichmann 2014, pp. 25-26.

Pl. 2.3.2: Detail of fresco from tomb of Nebamun, 18th Dynasty, c. 1350 BCE, Thebes, Egypt. Lute Type A on right, Type B on left. Author: unknown; photo in Public Domain. Source: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Egyptian_lute_players_001.jpg

The two types share most of their design elements. Both are usually¹² *half-spike* or *tang lutes*; the *pole*, that part of the neck that extends through the resonator's central axis from the *shoulders* down, ends short of the interior wall of the resonator's base in a *spike*. The soundboards or faces are made of rawhide, probably goat, soaked until malleable then stretched across the hollow resonator and affixed to the sides.

As observed on the lute of Harnosě, the luthier makes several width-wise cuts into the hide and weaves the pole through them so that alternating strips support the pole from below and press it down from above. As the hide dries and tightens, the alternating pressure of these

¹² The Harnosě lute uses a full spike design although tomb frescoes generally seem to indicate half-spikes.

strips holds the pole firmly in place, level with the plane of the rim. The luthier also cuts a hole near the hide's lower end to allow the spike's tip to protrude so they can attach the looped string-ends to the spike; they then run the strings over the bridge and up the neck, then tie the strings' other ends to leather tuning rings wrapped around the instrument's *head*.

The Egyptian lutes' bridges (*Pl. 2.3.1*) followed an ingenious and nearly unique design neither 'floating' as on a banjo or *tanbūr* nor glued on, as on guitars and *ʿūd*s. Rather, these wooden bridges are horizontally fan-shaped, wide at the front where the strings' vibrating lengths begin, narrowing as they near the spike, and fitted with a notch that 'is attached to the end of the neck by an underlapping joint.'¹³

At the shoulders, the neck is not mortised into the resonator wall as on most modern instruments but simply rests on the wall's rim. This results in a high bulge in the soundboard where the pole weaves through it instead of lying flat and parallel to the resonator's rim. The leather cord or rawhide strips that form the tuning rings are tied around the head using one of several methods. The luthier knots the string-end to one end of the cord and wraps a piece of linen cloth around the knot to secure it so it does not slip under the cord as they tighten the string (*Pl. 2.3.3*). The musician tunes their lute by sliding each ring up or down until they reach the desired pitch. With a little practice one can use these rings to tune with fine precision, and in my experience I have found that once 'broken in' they will hold their tuning astonishingly well, often much better than friction or geared tuners.

¹³ Scott, 1944, p. 162.

Pl. 2.3.3: Lute of Harmosē head showing upper string-ends and tuning rings. Scott, 1944, p. 161.

2.4: Organology of West African Sahelian Lutes

The lutes of the West Africa Sahel grasslands (*Pl. 2.4.1*) form a distinct family among other lute types and show little influence from Arab chordophones in their design or social roles.¹⁴ They do, however, display striking organological similarities to the ancient Egyptian lutes of the oblong Type B that, while not constituting proof of direct descent from the latter, seems too great to attribute to mere coincidence. Demonstrating a lineal descent from Egypt to the Sahel is difficult, as the Egyptian types considered here disappeared from the historical record by the Hellenistic era and the earliest notices of West African lutes come from Arab travelers nearly 1,000 years later. This huge gap in documented evidence obviously makes any lute transmission process between the two regions opaque. Thus the organological similarities speak perhaps even more loudly for some kind of historical connection.

¹⁴ The Sahelian musical system is also largely endemic, though certain individual players have been known to use modified elements of Arab *maqām* in their playing.

Pl. 2.4.1: Example of Sahelian lute; Mauritanian *tidinit*, made before c. 1955. Author's photo.

Sahelian lutes go by many different names throughout West Africa, depending on the language and culture of the users (Fig. 2.4.1): Mandé speakers call theirs *ngoni* whereas Wolof speakers refer to it as *xalam*, the Fulani as *hoddu*, and in Mauritania it is the *tidinit*, perhaps related to the Touareg *tehardin(t)*.¹⁵ Finally, the Gnaoua of Morocco and Tunisian Stambali sect use the name *guembri* or *sintir*. But whatever their regional names or social roles these various species remain morphologically consistent with one another. They all consist of a long, narrow, oblong body with a long, rounded handle inserted into the goat hide soundboard using a half-spike method, and strings attached to the head with leather tuning rings.

The primary differences consist of, first, the number of strings—the whole genus contains two long strings that are stopped with the left hand, but species will have anywhere from one (*tehardint*) to six (Senegambian *ngoni* and *xalam*) additional strings affixed to tuning rings positioned between the neck's mid-point and its shoulders.

Second, the resonator's walls typically are carved surprisingly thick—as much as a full centimeter—and the resonator itself shows an oblong shape, although the Mauritians *tidinit* has considerably thinner walls and a slight indent that gives the body a 'waisted' profile. This oblong shape, waisted or straight, strongly recalls the Type B

¹⁵ For ethnographic and ethnomusicological discussions of these instruments and their complex social and cultural roles, see Charry (2000); Coolen 1983; Shoup 1997.

Egyptian lute's appearance and is not common outside these two areas.¹⁶

Fig. 2.4.1: Map of Sahel region.¹⁷

Third, as a matter of regional style the goat hide soundboard may be attached to the resonator using wooden pegs metal nails, or one of several methods of lashing with rawhide thongs or rope.

Fourth, in some regions, particularly among the Fulani, players will attach a metal sheet edged with metal rings onto an iron nail driven into their lute's head; the vibrations of the plucked strings rattle the

¹⁶ Certain Caucasus lutes such as the Avar *panduri*, and the so-called 'boat' or 'trough' shaped lutes of Southeast Asia and the Pacific, like the *hasapi*, have long narrow resonators that superficially resemble this oblong form, but otherwise diverge in many important ways from the Egyptian and Sahelian genera.

¹⁷ Source: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Map_of_the_Sahel.png; accessed on 20 Mar. 2022. Licensed under Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 Unported, available at <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/legalcode>. Author: Munion. All text and labels on map are modifications made by myself, Jeffrey P Charest, 20 Mar. 2022.

rings against the sheet and color the instrument's tone with a metallic buzz.

Fifth, these instruments come in an array of sizes, from the Mandé *ngoni* at about 23-25" to the Fulani or Mauritanian species and North African *guembri*, a bass instrument, that average nearly 3'.¹⁸

The final important difference lies in the tuning systems and certain ornamental techniques that differ from culture to culture. These do not appreciably affect the lute's design or construction, which runs thusly: the maker carves out the interior of a piece of wood with an adze. They soak a piece of raw goat hide in water, sometimes with hair still on it, and stretch it across the hollowed resonator. The luthier cuts a hole in the hide at the instrument's shoulders and another one near its base; the handle—the neck and pole as one unit—with rounded fingerboard like that of the Egyptian lute, is inserted through the shoulder-hole and rests directly on the body's upper rim, again as in Egypt.

However, unlike Egypt's lutes, here the pole is not woven through a series of slits cut in the hide but simply straight through from shoulders to the hole near the base. The result of this procedure is that as the skin dries and tightens its tension causes the pole to tilt downward towards the base instead of remaining parallel to the body's rim.

Pl. 2.4.2: additional strings on tidinit run on either side of primary pair, on a slightly lowered plane. Author's photo.

¹⁸ Since the 1990s several *ngoni* players such as Bassekou Kouyate or Makan Badje Tounkara, both from Mali, have introduced innovations on *ngoni* design, such as commissioning a new bass version of the lute to facilitate *ngoni* ensemble playing, a performance innovation.

This slight change in method was probably preceded, and made necessary, by a significant innovation made to Sahelian lutes that truly distinguishes them from their theoretical Egyptian forebears: the addition of strings beyond the two or three primary, stopped strings (*Pl. 2.4.2*). These additional strings run along both sides of the central pair, tuned as extensions of the pitch range produced by the stopped strings, and played somewhat in the manner of a harp or lyre rather than a lute.

Because they are tuned to higher pitches these strings must be shorter than the primary pair and so their tunings rings sit below those of the primaries. As a result, if the neck and pole's plane remained level, these extra rings would inadvertently act as frets when the musician stops the primary strings, thereby diminishing their available range (*Fig. 2.4.2, A-B*).

Pl. 2.4.3: Ringed vertical fan bridge of ngoni. Author's photo.

To prevent this, the primary strings' action—the distance between string and fingerboard—needed to be raised so that when pressed down, the strings would still clear the lower tuning rings and vibrate freely. Therefore, as the pole angles downwards towards the body's base the neck angles upwards towards the head.

A full resolution of this problem with the action, however, required a second, complementary innovation from Sahelian luthiers (*Fig. 2.4.2, C*): rather than a notched, horizontally aligned fan bridge they created a vertically aligned fan bridge, carved into a ring at its lower end and slid *onto* the spike instead of into it (*Pl. 2.4.3*). When assembled, the bridge is pulled forward by the strings' pressure and raises them several centimeters above the soundboard (*Pl. 2.4.4*). The neck's upwards angle lessens the strings' angle as they approach the head so that their action is comfortably low to the upper fingerboard

but still high enough at their mid-point to clear the lower tuning rings when the musician stops them.

*Fig. 2.4.2: A) String action on New Kingdom lute with horizontal bridge.
B) Addition of tuning rings for new strings obstructs string vibration.
C) Angled handle and vertical bridge clears obstruction by raising action.*

Pl. 2.4.4: Side view of tidinit showing string action. Author's photo.

On the one hand, the Sahelian lutes' similarities to Egypt's Type B made them valuable models for reconstructing the Elamite-

Mesopotamian *tigidla*, the latter's assumed ancestor. On the other hand, their morphological differences and design innovations illustrated a key principle, or perhaps a caveat, that I have and will continue to follow when undertaking such reconstructions: that one seemingly small change to an instrument's design, like adding one or more strings, can necessitate a series of changes to other elements.

2.5: Organology of North African *gunbri/loutar* Lutes

My third set of models, the North African *gunbri/loutar* genus (Pl. 2.5.1), tend to visually strongly resemble the Egyptian Type A, smaller lute and the later Hellenistic type, with their generally rounded resonators, shorter necks relative to Type B, and overall smaller proportions. The *gunbri* species feature resonators most commonly made of wood although tortoise shell is frequently used—another commonality with the Egyptian lute—and, less often, gourd. Especially with their goat hide soundboards, rounded fingerboards and spike construction they pre-date the introduction of Arab lutes like the *ʿūd* with its wooden soundboard, flat fingerboard and ribbed construction and mortised neck. In fact, regional legends Morocco to Arabia speak of an ancestral or original *ʿūd* with a hide soundboard.¹⁹

Pl. 2.5.1: Moroccan *gunbri*. Photo by Zara and Marek Case, used by permission.

A physical line of transmission probably lies in the extensive contacts and colonization of the North African coast by Phoenicians

¹⁹ Some of these legends claim that the famous Arab Andalusian musician Ziryab originally played one of these and invented the wooden soundboard after his *ʿūd* was damaged by mice. See Farmer 1929/1994, p. 15.

and other eastern Mediterranean peoples since the Bronze Age. Furthermore, the so-called Hellenistic and Roman era ‘Coptic lute’,²⁰ represented by seven physical specimens excavated from sites along the Nile River, also features in Libyan and Tunisian iconography from the 6th century CE.²¹ Thus a conduit for musical instrument transmission clearly ran from or through Egypt to the western Mediterranean. The idea, then, of a direct connection from Egyptian Type A lutes to the Berber *gunbri* and *loutar* et. al., with distinct design modifications at later periods, seems to me a reasonable assumption.

Nevertheless, morphologically the Berber lutes have drifted further from their putative Egyptian ancestors than the Sahelian examples in two key ways. First, this genus typically bears floating bridges not attached to the spike at all (*Pl. 2.5.2*), although many species retain the half-spike construction with the string-ends tied to notches on the spike’s tip. In fact, on some species such as the Amazigh *loutar* the pole extends through the full length of the body and rests on the base’s rim via a notch cut into the pole’s underside so that it sits flush with the rim instead of resting on top of it.

*Pl. 2.5.2: Floating bridge of gunbri.
Photo by Zara and Marek Case, used
by permission.*

The second example of this morphological drift lies in the *gunbri*-s’ use of wooden tuning pegs instead of leather tuning rings to tune the two to four wound gut strings. Both of these elements—bridge and tuners—almost certainly represent much more recent

²⁰ See Eichmann 1994.

²¹ Qasr’ al-Libia, mosaics of a Byzantine church in Theodorias (formerly Olbia) refounded by Emperor Justinian (r. 527-565). See Winternitz 1961, pp. 228-229.

(i.e. within the last ~2,000 years) developments of the instrument's form.

Because of these modifications I have referred less to this group of models than the other two; however, the *gunbri* specimens I have examined provided useful comparative information on factors such as how changes in the pole's position and transit through the hide soundboard affects the neck's angle, the strings' action, frettable string length, and bridge height.

2.6: Constructing the *Tigidla*: Taking Measurements

My first step in planning and constructing the Elamite-Mesopotamian *tigidla* was to deduce the instrument's probable dimensions. In her catalogue of these Elamite figurines Sepideh included complete measurements of each of the figures and their lutes (when possible); after selecting representative examples from each of her seven categories, I compiled a table of what I considered the most pertinent dimensions—height, shoulder widths and arm lengths of the dwarf figures, and lengths and widths of each lute and their necks and resonators (*Appendix A*). I enlarged some of the photographs and measured these same aspects in order to record them in finer detail in order to scale the reconstruction's dimensions up or down and maintain the same proportions of the figurines' lutes. I then averaged out these sets of measurements, including the relative sizes of the lutes to the players' bodies as well.

As seen in the photographs in *Appendix A* these Elamite lutes (*Pl. 2.6.1*) presents a representative example), despite any regional or individual differences, follow the same essential form: a long straight neck of moderate width that seems to penetrate the small, round resonator. The poles generally do not run all the way through the body but seem to stop somewhere past the soundboard's midpoint. On some figurines the pole terminates in a roughly triangular shape slightly wider than pole's edges, but on others the pole seems to simply end; I have generally interpreted these as a half-spike construction comparable to those of the New Kingdom and Sahelian lutes.

Pl. 2.6.1: Elamite figurine LNL A:007. Photo by Sepideh Khaksar, used by permission.

Some Elamite examples indicate that the pole was raised above the plane of the body's rim and soundboard, as on the Egyptian examples, though I detect little indication of the 'weaving' technique. Instead, the Elamite pole seems to simply run down the central axis of the lute's face. The 'raised' effect could be due to how the Elamite artisans modeled their clay and should not be construed as a reliable organological detail. Some of the images, in fact, model the soundboard as merely a smooth disk with no sign that the handle extends past the lute's shoulders. For that matter, as Sepideh observes, some examples do not even display any strings!

Others, fortunately, clearly bear two additional lines in between and parallel to those of the neck to represent strings. Finally, most of the examples display two coiled or braided ropes with tasseled ends that dangle from the headstock. Most scholars consider these to be ornamental cords tied to the ends of two tuning rings, although it must be pointed out that the tuning rings themselves are rarely clearly shown outside of Egyptian examples. In many cases the area of the headstock is broken off or badly damaged which somewhat complicates the interpretation this area's construction.

The precise lute-dimensions and proportions of my sample set showed a considerable degree of variation; this agrees with Sepideh's theory that these instruments had no universally standard form but were fashioned according to regional or individual tastes. The only truly certain elements were the longish neck and the small round resonator, or rather a round soundboard, as the resonator itself is indeterminate for reasons discussed below. I thus assumed that these *tigidla* could be scaled to an individual's body size as long as the lutes retained the same basic proportions among its various parts, namely resonator and neck.

Despite the size-range of these *tigidla* the essential proportions of (RL) to resonator width (RW), from 1:1 to 1:2 (occasionally as much as 2:3), remained fairly consistent. Proportions of resonator length to neck length (RL: NL) were less so, and ran from 1:4 to 1:9. However, the wider spectrum of (RL):(NL) ratios compared to that of (RL):(RW) gave me some latitude with scaling the neck length to the resonator dimensions (*Table B*).

(RL): (NL)	1:4	1:5	1:6	1:7	1:8	1:9
(TL) (Total Length)	600 mm.	625 mm.	720 mm.	875 mm.	960 mm.	108 mm.

Table 2.6.1: Spectrum of resonator to neck-length ratios and corresponding total instrument lengths.

From this data I drew up a 'life-size' blueprint from which to work out body curvature, neck dimensions, resonator depth etc. Much of this planning was improvised and experimental—I became aware of how I was, in the process of recreating a historical, long-extinct instrument also inventing a new one. Another limitation at this stage was that my reconstruction had to stay within the diameters and qualities of the wood I had available to work with. In this I probably operated under greater constraints than an Elamite craftsman who, if they worked in a workshop attached to court or temple, as in Mesopotamia,²² was likely to have stockpiles of wood to choose from.

²² Several documents from Mesopotamia attest to the presence of royal workshops dedicated to instrument-making, overseen by a *gala* priest from the temple and of music teachers who provided lessons to children of

The wood I used for the resonator was a block of plane tree or ‘false sycamore’, *Acer pseudoplatanus*, measuring 90 mm. wide x 95 mm. long and 70-90 mm. deep that I sawed from a larger block. (For the neck I used a length of European beech, *Fagus sylvatica*, from an up-cycled chair leg.) The complete block had been cut from a dead sycamore and air dried for about 2-3 years.

Plane or sycamore was a fortunate find, as it has historical precedent for use in carpentry and woodworking in Mesopotamia and Egypt.²³ In both locales it was mostly imported and so perhaps something of a luxury item, although plane trees were more readily available than more ‘exotic’ species such as rosewood or ebony from India or Lebanese cedar.

2.7: The *tigidla* construction process

I then began preparing the sycamore block for the resonator. Using a saw rasp, wood files and chisels I roughly shaped the outside of the bowl. At this stage I decided to add some inlaid ornaments on the outside of the bowl and cut grooves along the edges where the inlays would fit into place (*Pl. 2.7.1*). Considering the Mesopotamian evidence that lutes formed part of the court instrumentarium,²⁴ I saw little reason to only create a basic-looking instrument and felt it appropriate to ‘dress it up’ to suit its original social and cultural environment.

administrative officials. See Michalowski 2006, pp. 50, 58, and 2010, pp.204-206.

²³ NB this species is not to be confused with the unrelated *Ficus sycomorus*, or fig tree, which is native to the Middle East but seldom, as far as I have found, used for woodworking. *Acer pseudoplatanus*'s native range extended from Eastern Europe as far south as the Levant, and was fairly common in ancient furniture and other uses.

²⁴ See Michalowski, 2006, p.58. In addition, Ur III King Šulgi (r. c. 2094-c.2046 BCE) lists a *šukara* lute among the instruments he learned how to play as part of his official music training and accomplishments (Castellino, 1972, p. 47).

Pl. 2.7.1: Exterior of rough-shaped resonator.

Pl. 2.7.2: Resonator interior with inlay grooves. Author's photos.

When the rough shaping on the outside had reached a satisfactory stage I began hollowing out the inside (*Pl. 2.7.2*) using gouges, a spoon-carver's scorp, an adze and a wood borer. I used the wood borer to drill holes into the area to be hollowed to facilitate the adzing and gouging process and prevent the wood from splitting in unwanted directions.

When I felt the walls had reached an appropriate thickness I returned to fine-shaping the exterior. This allowed me to make the walls slightly thinner than I could from just working the inside. I then needed to repair the crack that ran across the body near the bottom so it would not spread any further and so I cut some 'butterfly' splints, so-called because they resemble the spread wings of a butterfly (*Pl. 2.7.3*), from bone. The narrow mid-section of the splints fits onto the crack and the widening triangular sections act as a brace to hold the two sides of the crack in place and prevent the wood from opening up again. I inlaid these splints along the length of the cracks and glued them in place with hide glue, then used a glue and sawdust paste to fill in the cracks. Because I like to err on the side of caution, I glued an additional strip of hide in the bowl's interior along the crack.²⁵

²⁵ A similar technique is used for such repairs for violins and cellos, except luthiers will typically use round patches of parchment/vellum, a type of fine paper made from processed animal hide.

Pl. 2.7.3: Back of finished resonator showing ebony inlays and bone 'butterfly' splints across span of crack. Author's photo.

When the resonator was shaped I treated it inside and out with a solution of warm water and boric acid powder as a non-toxic and effective protection against wood-borer beetles, to which sycamore is especially vulnerable.

Pl. 2.7.4: Mock-up of shaped handle and resonator. Author's photo.

I then cut out, shaped and installed the inlays that I made from a piece of Mun ebony, *Diospyrus mun*,²⁶ whose dark, almost black

²⁶ This species comes from Vietnam and Laos and is not on the CITES list for woods illegal to export.

color formed a pleasing and dynamic contrast with the pale sycamore (Pl. 2.7.3). I filed and sanded the inlays down so their edges blended smoothly with the contours of the bowl, then gave the entire piece a final polishing with progressively finer grades of sandpaper (180-5,000 grits).

I then cut and rounded the neck using a hollowed wood plane, spoke shave, a flat adze and a knife (Pl. 2.7.4). My intended diameter for the neck started off as 17.5 mm., 2.5 mm. narrower than what my measurements suggested, but I opted for a smaller diameter due to the soundboard's width. Unfortunately, I overshot my mark at one point and so I was forced to continued carving until I reached a consistent 15 mm. diameter. This works well enough as a fingerboard but on future versions of the *tigidla* I will keep to a diameter between 17.5 and 20.5 mm.

I cut a notch in the middle of the spike's end to form two protrusions where the strings would loop around before passing over the bridge (Pl. 2.7.5). Egyptian luthiers used this method, although not exclusively, and it is found on most *gunbri* as well.²⁷

Pl. 2.7.5: Notched end of *tigidla* spike with looped strings.
Author's photo.

I also worked out a method to install the copper rings that would replicate the perpendicular lines observed on the necks of some figurines, that may or may not have indicated frets (see below). I inset these bands into the neck using melted shellac as an adhesive and bending the copper into the grooves I had cut for them (Pl. 2.7.6). I painted the spaces in-between these

²⁷ The Sahelian *ngoni/xalam* instruments, on the other hand, pad their string ends with thread and wrap them around the conical spike-tip, in elaborate fashion, before tying them off and passing them over the bridge.

bands with my own homemade paint of ground lapis lazuli, egg yolk, some water and a dash of vinegar as a preservative.²⁸

*Pl. 2.7.6: Insetting copper bands to neck with melted shellac.
Author's photo.*

When I had finished all the preparatory work on the resonator and handle I began assembling the two (*Pl. 2.7.7a-b*) and readying the accouterments such as the bridge, tuning rings, tasseled cords, strings and plectrum. All of this required a series of executive decisions on my part that I describe in the next section.

Pl. 2.7.7a: Top view of assembled tigidla.

²⁸ Lapis lazuli was a highly valued mineral in the Ancient Near and Middle East and was imported all the way from its source in modern day Badakhshan, in extreme northern Afghanistan and the western region of Tajikistan. While I am happy with its appearance I would not repeat this technique on further *tigidla*, as there is, sadly, no satisfactory way to seal the paint to fully protect it from chipping, rubbing or scratching.

Pl. 2.7.7b: Assembled tigidla, side views. Author's photos.

2.8: Open possibilities of design issues

Due to the limitations of my iconographic sources, many design elements required educated guesswork. Because this first reconstruction was a prototype I had a certain degree of latitude to experiment with different possibilities, especially with the following aspects:

Spike/pole: the iconography *seems* to display a half-spike construction like those of my New Kingdom and Sahelian models but I have considered that this may simply have been an iconographic convention to convey where the bridge sat, with any further details deemed unnecessary to the image's purpose. I chose a half-spike method without the Egyptian 'weaving' technique—but with some consequences discussed below.

Pl. 2.8.1: Rounded fingerboard of tigidla.

Contour of neck and fingerboard (Pl. 2.8.1): the fingerboard is generally assumed to be rounded as opposed to flat like most modern fingerboards. This assumption stems from the examples of the New

Kingdom lutes as well as the fact that, a few East Asian specimens aside, the vast majority of spiked or half-spiked lutes also possess rounded fingerboards. The Sahelian lutes, the *gunbri/loutar*, and bowed spike lutes like the Iranian *kamānča*, Turkish *qabak kemençe*, and Chinese *erhu* all attest to this trend. As the Elamite-Mesopotamian iconography strongly indicate a spiked construction I assumed this to be the case here as well.

Pl. 2.8.2: Detail of tigidla shoulders showing half-inset construction. Author's photo.

Shoulders (Pl. 2.8.2): did the neck rest on the upper rim of the body at shoulders like those of my models or was it mortised or inset into the rim? Since a half-spike construction seemed correct the former choice seemed most appropriate, although in the end I opted for a partially inset neck, also with some consequences.

Pl. 2.8.3: Tigidla soundboard, pericardial membrane of sheep or goat. (Slight tear near shoulders is recent damage incurred during transport.) Author's photo.

Soundboard (Pl. 2.8.3): following all three of my models I concluded that the soundboard was made of animal hide rather than wood, but the

type and quality of hide remains unknown. Though it was most likely goat or perhaps sheepskin, for the prototype I experimented with the kind of covering used for *tar* lutes in modern Iran and Azerbaijan. *Tar* soundboards are made of either the hide of fetal, usually stillborn sheep or goats, or the pericardial (heart) membrane. Both are very fine-grained, thin, almost translucent materials with as much strength and vibration transmitting power as goat hide.

Bridge (Pl. 2.8.4): while the triangular shape at the terminal point in some Elamite cases resembles the Egyptian horizontal fan-shaped bridges, it is also conceivable that it represents either a kind of tailpiece or a bridge affixed to what would then be a wooden, not hide, soundboard. While ancient lute images of instruments with such a bridge do exist they date, at earliest, from the Parthian or the Hellenistic eras or, respectively, from c. 200 BCE and 332 BCE on. It should be noted that Ancient Near Eastern lute bridges are never clearly shown until the 1st millennium BCE, and even then only rarely.

Pl. 2.8.4: Floating bridge of *tigidla*, carved from *Bubinga* wood, *Guibourtia* spp. probably *G. demeusii*. Author's photo.

Because the triangular shape is common but not universal on the Elamite images; that the extant Egyptian lutes use such a bridge, and because of the latters' royal and aristocratic performance contexts, a certain conservativeness could be assumed regarding the form of the lute after its introduction to Egypt. If so, then one can further assume

that Egyptian bridge design followed that of its northern source and my original plan called for a horizontal fan-bridge, albeit I did not decide on a notched or ringed design at that time.

While assembling the *tigidla*, however, my half-spike construction method presented some problems. The resonator's short axis and the need for a long enough spike to loop the strings onto without it touching the interior wall of the base, meant that the spike had insufficient space for a notched or ringed fan-bridge. Additionally, the front edge of such a bridge, where the strings pass over, would sit too far forward on the soundboard for proper sound transmission to take place; in my experiments this resulted in a 'thin' or tinny tone with few low-range harmonics and poor volume. In the end the best alternative was a floating bridge that I could adjust to find the optimal spot—roughly 1/3rd up the soundboard from the base—to produce a good balance of bass-treble harmonics and maximum volume.

A second problem resulting from this construction was that after inserting the pole into the damp hide, as the hide dried and tightened the increasing pressure pushed the pole downward so that it no longer touched the soundboard—an essential condition for sound transmission. My experiments suggested that this was in part due, again, to the resonator's short axis. After considerable fiddling about I managed to resolve this issue but in future attempts I will use a full-spike method like that of the *loutar* described above.

Resonator (Pl. 2.8.5): there are no ancient Near Eastern lute images that give any sign of what these lutes' backs looked like, how deep/shallow they were, or how thick or thin the walls were carved. The Egyptian artifacts demonstrate that their resonators, were hollowed from a single block of wood to a depth of between 5-15 cm., and the *ngoni*, *gunbri* and *loutar* do so as well. In conjunction with this is the fact that the 'ribbing' technique as used on modern European lutes or Arabic *ūd* originated as late as the Medieval period, and that modern Near Eastern lutes like some Kurdish *tanbūr* constructed this way follow a late 19th or 20th century innovation.

Pl. 2.8.5: Detail of *tigidla* resonator, side view. Author's photo.

The vast majority of ANE and Egyptian images show lutenists holding their instrument in the crook of their right arm, so one can infer that the body was at least deep enough to facilitate this. In line with this evidence, and to maximize the sound chamber of my fairly small piece of sycamore wood, I utilized the full depth of the block, about 9 cm. I carved the upper walls to a thickness of approximately 5 mm. or less, gradually thickening them to about 5-10 mm. towards the bottom. I could have carved them thinner but decided not to, to avoid exacerbating the natural crack in the wood; future version of the *tigidla* will be carved thinner to see how that affects tone and volume.

I also assumed that the bowl would roughly resemble those of the modern *tanbūr/tambura*. This assumption was not entirely conscious, but was conditioned by my findings in my Thesis research that as a general rule the depth of an instrument's body lies in inverse proportion to the width of the soundboard; thus a modern *tanbūr*'s soundboard runs roughly 15-20 cm. and sound chamber depth to about 20-30.5 cm., whereas a Chinese *pipa* has a sound chamber only 7.6 cm. deep but a soundboard at least a full 30.5 cm. across.²⁹

²⁹ Exceptions to this do exist, notably the so-called 'boat' or 'trough'-shaped lutes of the Indonesian *hasapi* family, the Avar *panduri*, and the Afghan *rubab*. On all of these, however, the very narrow soundboard is usually paired with an

Strings: the common Akkadian term *pitnu* points to the use of strings made of twisted gut and/or animal sinew, and the Harnosē lute was found with two, possibly three, relatively intact gut strings both with a diameter of about 1 mm. As far as I am aware no studies have been conducted on how these strings were made but those of the modern Gnaoua *guembri/sintir* and Indian bowed instruments like *sarangi* often purposely contain fragments of veins and other tissue in them.

These are not generally as finely wound and polished as the gut strings made for European Early Music instruments, which are sometimes even varnished or shellacked. This results not from any ‘primitive’ methods or skills but because this manner of gut string construction lends them the culturally desired acoustic tone and texture, what Kurt Sachs and Lawrence Picken have termed the *Klangideal*.³⁰ How the Mesopotamians, Elamites et. al. made their strings and what kind of *Klangideal* they sought from their instruments is, probably, unrecoverable.

Due to reasons of convenience and expense, for my prototype *tigidla* I opted to use European-style gut strings of .54 and .62(?) diameters, although in the future I will experiment with hand-fashioned *sintir* strings (available on eBay from Morocco) and eventually with making my own gut strings.

To attach the upper string-ends to the tuning rings I imitated the method used on the Harnosē lute as closely as possible. I tied the ends to small wooden blocks and then wrapped these with cotton cloth (*Pl.* 2.8.6). I knotted this bundle to a knot on one end of the tuning ring and then looped this around the lute’s head in the manner utilized on Sahelian lutes (*Pl.* 2.8.7).

unusually deep, barrel-chested sound chamber and, significantly, an extremely elongated resonator that may continue into the neck.

³⁰ Picken 1975, pp. 564-565.

Pl. 2.8.6: Upper string ends tied to wooden blocks and wrapped in cotton cloth. Author's photo.

Pl. 2.8.7: String ends tied to leather tuning rings and affixed to tigidla head. Author's photo

Frets proved the most contentious aspect of the reconstruction process, one that Sepideh and I debated at great length. Two of her seven categories of Elamite figurines display perpendicular lines across the lute necks on several she examined. She maintained that they could be frets, a reasonable hypothesis given how little we know of ANE tuning systems and the rather slippery nature of the issue even in modern times; for example, although the Persian *dastgāh*, Arabic *maqām*, and Turkish *makam* musical systems all share elements in common, notably the use of $\frac{1}{4}$ tones, each system measures these $\frac{1}{4}$ tones differently, the Persian being the narrowest intervals and the Turkish the widest. Such fractional differences would be effectively impossible to notice, let alone determine, from any but the most scientifically precise images of these cultures' respective lutes.

Furthermore, I noticed that the spacing of these lines on specimens from Sepideh's Group D category of figurine are highly inconsistent with each other. The lines on some members of Group D were spaced fairly regularly with a group of three in the middle of the neck and similar groups placed symmetrically at either end. The other type of lines, on the other hand, clustered irregularly on the upper end of the neck.

I therefore contended that, even if they do represent frets, the artisans were not attempting to create realistic models of the instruments and that the lines cannot provide accurate guides to what scale(s) these instruments might have used.

Eventually we conditionally agreed on a hypothesis: that the lines were ornaments etched or painted onto the neck, not protruding like a true fret. They may have thereby marked *tonal regions* to delimit where a musician could find, say, the second degree of the scale, but could adjust the exact pitch according to modal requirements. An analogy here could be the Aristoxenian concept of the *pyknis*, the two microtonal intervals that occupied the interior of a tetrachord and were measured not by strict ratios but by ranges. The more or less exact placing of the *pyknis* depended on what species of tetrachord—chromatic, diatonic, or enharmonic—one was playing in.

This hypothesis of course assumes many things, such as whether Elamite musicians played modally; if their notion of modes bore any resemblance to our current understandings of such, or if they even conceived of a 'scale' as a thing capable of being abstracted from functional melodies. Considering the vagaries of the two types of line groupings, it also assumes that they utilized microtones in their music, but as no information exists as to Elamite music theory or practice these matters remain purely conjecture.³¹

³¹ The so-called Hurrian music theory and tuning texts provide some information but it is an open question as to how widely used these texts were or if they only held for music practice at that time and place (Michalowski, 2010, pp. 207-217). Hagel (2005, pp. 312=317) has argued for the use of tempered, i.e. impure or 'just' thirds in the tuning system. It is also worth noting that some regions of the Near and Middle East incorporate numerous $\frac{1}{4}$ tones of varying sizes, such as Arabic and Ottoman maqām/makam music—both also influenced by the Pythagorean tuning in pure 5ths—and the Iranian dastgāh system. There are, however, tuning systems distinctly non-Pythagorean such as what is called

On this hypothesis I re-measured the lines in question on one figurine (D:001) as accurately as I could and scaled them to the length of my *tigidla* neck. I found that they did approximate the positions of the second, fifth and upper fourth degrees, but only roughly and only after I somewhat altered their positions.

In my opinion, these rings probably do not determine an Elamite ‘scale’ although they can be provisionally used as a generalized guide to certain interval positions. One could certainly reconfigure them as such, and I may do so on future versions, were I to make some for commercial purposes. But I would not feel comfortable claiming them as historically accurate.³² Whether the Elamites or Mesopotamians intended them as such remains yet another probably unanswerable question.

the ‘Georgian Common tuning’ (cit.) based on an equidistant heptatonic scale of non-Equal Tempered whole tones of about ~171 cents each (Tseretele and Vashpidze 2015).

³² Shortly after finishing the instrument I did decide to add some tied-on gut frets. This was partly to compensate for a slight unevenness in the fingerboard that interfered with the clarity of certain pitches but also to experiment with some ideas on equidistant tunings that I had been thinking about. I make no claim to thus reconstructing an Elamite tuning, only to satisfy my curiosity. The results, in my estimation, are worth future refinements.

Appendix A: Table of Elamite Figurines Used for reconstruction

Object No.	Page No.	Thumbnail Image
LNL A:001	30	
LNL A:002	31	
LNL A:003	32	
LNL A:004	33	
LNL A:005	34	
LNL A:006	35	
LNL A:007	36	

LNL B:001	38	
LNL B:003	40	
LNL C:001	44	
LNL D:001	50	
LNL D:002	51	
LNL F:001 (Intersex)	56	
LNL H:003	63	

LNL I:008	71			
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Table A: Sample set of Elamite 'dwarf lutenists' used as models for lute recreation, compiled from Sepideh Khaksar's catalogue. (All photos and information used by permission of Sepideh Khaksar.)